

Performance of sorghum varieties in uncultivated lowland paddy

A. A. Gomez and A. A. Evangelista, Department of Agronomy, University of the Philippines at Los Baños, Philippines

In rainfed and partially irrigated rice areas, where water is limiting during the dry months, a logical cropping sequence is to grow rice during the rainy months and to follow it with drought-resistant upland crops during the dry months. Therefore, we tested the performance of 16 high-yielding sorghum varieties in uncultivated lowland puddled soil. By foregoing cultivation we avoided the difficult task of pulverizing a poorly structured soil. We were also able to plant immediately after the rice harvest and, most important, to use the substantial residual soil moisture for the growth of a second crop.

In spite of waterlogging at the early vegetative stage, four varieties – CS 100, CS 107, D 67-1, and D 674 – yielded higher than 4.0 t/ha (see table). These yields compare favorably with yields under normal upland culture.

Performance of 16 promising sorghum varieties grown in uncultivated lowland paddy soil. University of the Philippines at Los Baños (UPLB), Philippines, 1975–76 dry season.

Sorghum variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Blooming days	Plant ht (cm)
C 67-4	4.71	62	153
CS 100	4.66	66	134
CS 107	4.23	67	129
D 67-1	4.04	64	157
CS 108	3.71	63	132
CS 102	3.42	61	137
CS 106	3.42	61	147
CS 99	3.42	62	138
CS 105	3.33	62	126
CS 103	3.28	65	125
COSOR 3	3.23	65	145
IS 2940	3.04	64	171
139024	2.95	60	142
CS 104	2.90	67	121
498003	2.42	59	141
BPI SOR 1	1.66	62	151
Mean	3.40	63.12	140.56
Cv (%)	18.00	2.60	6.00
LSD .05	1.06	2.85	14.31

Invitation to authors

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two paragraphs and a table, figure, or photograph. They are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN. Duplicate prints of photos and illustrations are available to media on request from the Office of Information Services, IRRI. Persons who wish additional details of information presented in IRRN should write directly to the authors.

The International Rice Research Institute
P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines

